

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT
GPR	2010	B		Min: / Max: /	1300 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropic

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 1470-72 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: *Layers of preparation for info floor 1198*
 Covered by: SU: 1198 Fills: SU: Filled by: SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction
 FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX				
☒ Pottery M ☒ Nails R ☒ Tiles M ☐ Marble ☒ Amphorae R ☐ Quarried debris ☐ Dolia ☐ Slag ☐ Brick ☐ Mosaic tile(s) ☐ Basalt slabs ☐ Mortar ☐ Opus signinum ☐ Coins ☐ Painted plaster ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Burnt Adobe ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Other (specify) ☒ Glass R	☒ Tufo (specify) <i>crushed</i> ☐ Travertine <i>floor layer above</i> ☐ Other Limestone ☐ Basalt ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☒ Silt ☒ Pebbles (range) } ☒ Gravel (range) } <i>Marble sized to golf ball sized</i>	☐ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☒ Animal bones M ☐ Human bones ☐ Animal teeth ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)	clay 5% silt 70% sand 20% ☒ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive <table border="1"> <tr> <th>Compaction</th> <th>Color</th> </tr> <tr> <td> ☐ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft </td> <td> ☐ Black ☒ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify) </td> </tr> </table>	Compaction	Color	☐ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft	☐ Black ☒ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)
Compaction	Color						
☐ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft	☐ Black ☒ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)						

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)
 Northern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original
 Southern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Western Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Eastern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1198	Covers: 1321
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS: *hot, dry conditions. Next to wall btw rooms 2 and 3 is a rubble pile of medium to lg rocks.*

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: *northwestern part of Trench B 2010, Trench B, Room 3, North/central of excavation limit for trench B*
 Shape: *irregular*

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): *no slope*
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): *no clusks*
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): *stays the same*
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight
 Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping
 Cut bottom: flat concave irregular
 How is cut top edge? sharp rounded
 How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded
 Observations:

Key
 --- = Wall outline :::: = Crushed wall
 □ = Wall blocks # = Rocks
 /// = lower excavation/bedrock

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

preparation layer for info floor 1198 or a kind of filling/levelling activity in order to prepare the floor surface

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	CHM + JR	on	03.08.2010 / 23.6.2011
Revised by	CHM	on	03.08.2010
PDFd by	AAA	on	13.7.2011
Entered by		on	